

Dr Haris Muminović,
Docent,
Fakultet pravnih nauka,
Univerzitet Donja Gorica, Podgorica
Republika Crna Gora

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KRIVIČNOPRAVNA ZAŠTITA DECE MLAĐE OD 14 GODINA

Čovek je urođeni ljubavnik, izvor erosa, seksualno biće. Seksualnost je njegova osnovna karakteristika, a apetit za drugim ljudskim bićem, njegovo šesto čulo. U paradoksalnim objašnjenjima prefinjenosti percepcije šestog čula, seks i društvo su u stalnom, beskrajnom dvoboju, duboko ukorenjenom u istorijskoj diskurzivnoj nestabilnosti seksualnosti. Kroz istorijsku retoriku, ljudska priroda je okružena austom svetosti, ali atmosfera religiozne iracionalnosti, koja okružuje skoro svaki oblik intimnog ljudskog odnosa i, skoro vek nakon što je Čarls Darvin objavio „O poreklu vrsta“, nije uspela da objasni nasilnu prirodu ljudske vrste, obim i složenost nereproduktivnog seksualnog ponašanja i dubinu ljudskih emocija. Na takvoj osnovi, tvrdoglavi izraz da je seks istorijski bio „nevina oblast“ deluje kao sumnjiva igra reči da bi se podvukla važna, često previđena stvarnost. Dugo vremena, nauke su bile neprihvatljivo tihe pred pitanjima seksualnosti, pred percepcijom drugog „ja“ ljudskog života, pred saznanjem stranog nesvesnog i pokušajem da se odgovori na pitanja koja se tiču najdubljeg i najintimnijeg centra ljudskog bića. U celom procesu praćenom tišinom nauka, čudna praznina stepena do kog različita seksualna stanja bića mogu koegzistirati, izvršila je snažan uticaj u podsticanju objektivističke orijentacije nauka da otključaju jaz onoga što se smatra tabuom pod podsticanjem rigorozne distribucije polimorfne seksualnosti u korelaciji sa moralno prihvaćenim manifestacijama koje definišu pravu suštinu seksualnosti.

Ključne reči: krivična zaštita, seksualno zlostavljanje, pedofilija, registar osuđenih lica, devijantno ponašanje.

Haris Muminović, LL.D.,

Assistant Professor,

Faculty of Legal Sciences, University of Donja Gorica, Podgorica,

Republic of Montenegro

CRIMINAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN UNDER THE AGE OF 14

Man is an innate lover, the source of eros, a sexual being. Sexuality is one's fundamental characteristic, and the craving for another human being is one's sixth sense. In paradoxical explanations of the sophisticated perception of the sixth sense, sex and society are in a constant and eternal duel, deeply rooted in the historical discursive instability of sexuality. Through historical rhetoric, the human nature is surrounded by an aura of sanctity. Yet, almost a century after the publication of Charles Darwin's "On the Origin of Species", the atmosphere of religious irrationality, which is embodied in almost every form of intimate human relationship, has failed to explain the violent nature of the human species, the extent and complexity of non-reproductive sexual behavior, and the depth of human emotion. On these grounds, the stubborn statement that sex has historically been an "innocent domain" seems like a dubious play on words to underscore an important, often overlooked reality. For a long time, the sciences have been unacceptably silent on questions of sexuality, on the perception of the alter ego of human life, on the knowledge of the alien unconscious, and on the attempt to answer questions concerning the deepest and most intimate center of the human being. In the entire process accompanied by the silence of the sciences, the strange emptiness of the degree to which different sexual states of being can coexist has exerted a powerful influence in encouraging the objectivist orientation of the sciences to unlock the void of what is considered taboo under the encouragement of a rigorous distribution of polymorphic sexuality in correlation with the morally accepted manifestations that define the true essence of sexuality.

Keywords: criminal protection, sexual abuse, pedophilia, register of convicted persons, deviant behavior.